

SEMANTICS ON THE APPLICATION OF CORRELATION AND REGRESSION ANALYSES

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Abstract

Correlation analysis at the start considers the coexistence of at least bivariate data sets without attaching notion that one is dependent nor independent. The tool is used to determine the presence of linear association between or among interrelated variables. The linear association is measured in terms of correlation coefficient. The significance of the correlation coefficient is directly associated with the sample size. For data coming from continuous distributions, the sign of the correlation coefficient is vital. The methodology allows to find proxy variables from its highly correlated variables. This is the essence of multicollinearity analysis. The nonlinear or nonmonotonic relationship is extrinsic to such analysis. The regression analysis on the other hand assumes apriori information that the existence of a dependent variable is attributed with a distinct independent variable. A linear model is estimated to forecast future value of the dependent variable given corresponding values of the independent variable. Though correlation and regression analysis may have the same decision of rejecting their respective null hypotheses, nevertheless, they are two different things. The correlation speaks to mean that there exists linear association between two variables. While the regression analysis at one hand establishes a significant model, and second, provides an inference that speak to mean that the dependent variable changes by some unit per unit change in the independent variable through its regression coefficients. However, the use of correlation analysis aids in estimating a robust regression model.

Keywords: Correlation Coefficient, Regression Coefficients, Nonlinear, Monotonic, Multicollinearity, Robust.

I. RATIONALE

The correlation and regression analyses get into the picture when two or more variables coexist. The term correlation implies linear association between two or more variables. The existence of partial correlation is a consequence between two correlated variables given that the third variable coexist.

This is most particularly significant when the variables involved are measured in numeric scales. Most often, the term correlation is used in the context of a linear relationship between 2 continuous variables and expressed as Pearson product-moment correlation. The correlation coefficient is typically used for jointly normally distributed data (data that follow a bivariate normal distribution).

However, for rank data a particular measure of correlation is available (Schober, et. al, 2018). This comes like Spearman rank correlation. The correlation coefficient is a measure of strength on the linear association between variables and range from -1 to +1.

A negative one (-1) implies that the association has an inverse relationship. As one variable increases the other one tends to decrease. While the correlation of positive one (+1) implies that there is a perfect linear association between two variables. This speaks to mean that when one variable increases the other will also increase in the same direction. On the other hand, the regression analysis is geared toward model building. The basic idea is such that there is a priori information that one variable depends on one or more predictors variables.

This principle differs from the correlation analysis wherein variables involve coexist and no defined dependent or independent. Here, we can plot the scattered points and determine the most appropriate model. The use of least square method is always applied for its estimates are Uniformly Minimum Variance Unbiased Estimator.

The strength of the model is measured by the model coefficient of determination. For ease and simplicity of discussion between the correlation and regression analysis, simple regression model is considered in this review. This paper conveys the appropriate use of correlation and regression analysis foremost from their basic assumption down to the formulation of hypothesis.

This hypothesis provides the clarity of the ultimate objective of the investigation. Understanding the right objective allows the researchers to determine the right statistical methodologies. Thus, two methodologies with different applicability can be easily distinguish from each other. In like manner, that two different objectives pose two different solutions and consequential result of the analysis.

II. OBJECTIVE

This study intends to clarify applicability of methodologies and the suitable interpretation of the result of the analysis;

- 1) Illustrate hypothesis testing in correlation analysis
- 2) Illustrate hypothesis testing in regression analysis
- 3) Interpret correlation coefficient
- 4) Interpret regression coefficient and coefficient of determination

III. METHODOLOGY

A). Correlation Analysis

A few graphical representation of the different values of correlation coefficients.

1. Positive Correlation

2. Negative Correlation

3. Zero Correlation

The correlation coefficient is usually denoted in statistics by ρ_{xy} for a given variables x and y . It ranges from $-1 \leq \rho_{xy} \leq 1$. The sample correlation coefficient on the other hand is usually denoted by r_{xy} . The correlation coefficient indicates the degree of linear association between two variables. Thus, a hypothesized correlation coefficient of zero (0) is tested in the following sequence of steps.

i) Formulation of Hypothesis

$$H_0: \rho_{xy} = 0$$

with the suitable alternative hypothesis of the form

$$H_a: \rho_{xy} > 0$$

$$H_a: \rho_{xy} < 0$$

$$H_a: \rho_{xy} \neq 0$$

ii) Significance level (α)

iii) Test statistic

$$t_c = \frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{1-r^2}} \quad \text{eqn. (1)}$$

Where:

$$r = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}} \quad \text{eqn. (2)}$$

r is the sample correlation coefficient between variables x and y computed as

n is the number of paired observations

iv) Critical Region

Reject H_0 if $|t_c|$ is $> t_{(\alpha, df=n-2)}$, otherwise we retain the contention about the H_0 .

v) Decision

This is an immediate consequence of step iv.

vi) Conclusion

Either we reject H_0 or fail to reject H_0

The formulated hypothesis testing above would lead to make conclusion whether the correlation coefficient of the populations where, say x and y variables came from is significantly different from zero or not based from the available information from the sample. The significance of the correlation coefficient is strongly associated by the sample size.

Finally, the end result of correlation analysis is simply determination of existence of the linear association between two variables. Causation is none of the intricate result of said analysis. The finest information that can be generated through this analysis is such that one variable can be replaced with another variable in case they are significantly correlated. Further, the materiality of the analysis is to look for a meaningful variable that is inexpensive and readily available to serve as proxy for a variable that is unavailable or expensive to gather or to observe.

B). Regression Analysis

A model is oftentimes used by statistician as representative of a perceived ideal system (Walpole, 2012). A regression model finds its utility to forecast future value of the dependent variable based from the emerging patterns elucidated by the model. Estimating a simple linear regression model can be considered robust enough for its regression coefficient, the beta has the property of being Best Linear Unbiased Estimator (BLUE). Moreover, this model further assumes the homoscedasticity of the error term (Maddala, 2001).

$$y = \alpha + \beta x + \varepsilon \quad \text{eqn. (3)}$$

Where:

y - is the dependent variable

x - predictor, independent, regressor variable

α, β – regression coefficients

ε - $N(0, \sigma^2)$, the error term.

For a simple model, we have data of the form $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_n, y_n)$. The dependent variable y is estimated by \hat{y} and the coefficients are estimated by a for α and b for β . The estimated model has the form

$$\hat{y} = a + bx \quad \text{eqn. (4)}$$

Where:

$$b = \frac{\sum xy - (\sum x)(\sum y)/n}{\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2/n} \quad \text{eqn. (5)}$$

$$a = \frac{\sum y - b \sum x}{n} \quad \text{eqn. (6)}$$

The model is said to be significant whenever the beta coefficient b which estimates β is significantly different from zero. This means that the independent variable gives significant information about the dependent variable. Otherwise, when the beta coefficient b is not significantly different from zero, this means that the independent variable gives no information about the dependent variable. The hypothesis testing shall under go with the following sequence of steps:

i) Formulation of Hypothesis

$$H_0: \beta = 0$$

With the suitable alternative hypothesis of the form

$$H_a: \beta > 0$$

$$H_a: \beta < 0$$

$$H_a: \beta \neq 0$$

ii) Significance level (α)

iii) Test statistic

$$t_c = \frac{b-0}{s/\sqrt{s_{xx}}} \quad \text{eqn. (7)}$$

Where:

$$s^2 = \frac{\sum (y - \hat{y})^2}{n - 2} \quad \text{eqn. (8)}$$

$$s = \sqrt{s^2} \quad \text{eqn. (9)}$$

$$s_{xx}^2 = \sum (x - \bar{x})^2 \quad \text{eqn. (10)}$$

$$s_{xx} = \sqrt{s_{xx}^2} \quad \text{eqn. (11)}$$

iv) Critical Region

Reject H_0 if $|t_c|$ is $> t_{(\alpha, df=n-2)}$, otherwise we retain the contention about the H_0 .

v) **Decision**

This is an immediate consequence of step iv.

vi) **Conclusion**

Either we reject H_0 or fail to reject H_0

The coefficient of determination is given the percentage of the dependent variable that is attributed by the independent variable.

This measure is equal to 1 minus the ratio between the unexplained variation over the total variation of the model or simply it can be a squared correlation between observed dependent variable and the predicted y-variable. The equation below illustrate the computation of the coefficient of determination

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum (y - \hat{y})^2}{\sum (y - \bar{y})^2}. \quad \text{eqn. (12)}$$

The higher the value of the R^2 , the higher the accuracy of model prediction. However, valid interpretation regarding the coefficient of determination shall be consequential once the model is significant or the test for regression coefficient is significant. This is the fundamental issue about the use of regression analysis. This considers the logical structure of the model and the properties of being BLUE on the part of the model coefficients.

A hypothesis testing resulting to the rejection of the null hypothesis ($\beta \neq 0$) would mean that the dependent variable can be written as a linear function of the independent variable. This further provides an interpretation that the dependent variable would increase or decrease by b-unit(s) per unit increase or decrease of the independent variable. However, the retention of the null hypothesis would mean that the dependent variable is not attributed by any information from the independent variable.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Given the steps in hypothesis testing, the correlation and regression analyses have different null as well as their alternative hypotheses. Though the correlation and regression analyses yield to reject their respective null hypotheses, their respective interpretations are too different.

The correlation analysis touches the linear association between variables and the interchangeability between these associated variables. Neither it implies causality between them. Correlation does not imply causation (Janes, et.,al., 2021). Somehow, it can be interpreted as a linear communality between variables. The significant correlation coefficient would implies the presence of linear association.

Further interpretation would lead to conclude that one variable can serve as a proxy variable with one having significant correlation coefficient. In contrast, inference regarding

causality from two variables occurring together, without affecting each other is always misinterpreted.

The determination of causation will always be misunderstood as end product from the vantage correlation concept in which mistakes are easily made. Under the correlation analysis, both variables are assumed to be jointly distributed. The observed values of these variables are subject to natural random variation (Schober, et. al, 2018).

This review revealed that the significance of the correlation coefficient is strongly associated with the sample size as expounded in equation one (1). There is a possibility to reject the null hypothesis even if it is true with a large sample size.

In a linear regression analysis, the values of the independent variable are considered known constants. The analysis is generally used when fixed values of the independent variable are chosen from the investigators point of view in an experimental set-up. It estimates a significant model and determines how much of the dependent variable that is attributed based from the known values of the independent variable.

The significance of the regression coefficient would lead to conclusion that a dependent variable increase by an amount equivalent to regression coefficient per unit increase in the independent variable. The coefficient of determination R^2 measures the strength of the model and is based on the squared correlation between the actual values of the dependent variable and the predicted values of the dependent variables.

V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The correlation analysis varies significantly from the regression analysis. These two methodologies differ from each in terms of objective and associated interpretation at the end of the analytical result. The correlation analysis performs to determine the linear association between variables.

The higher the significance of the correlation speaks to mean that one variable can be substituted with the other variable. This gives light whenever proxy variable can be used in equally important analysis. However, when the relationship between variables is nonlinear or nonmonotonic, such relationship cannot be captured by correlation analysis. This limits correlation analysis to describe the nonlinear communality between variables.

On the other hand, the regression analysis formulates a model useful to determine the future value of the dependent variable based from significance of estimated parameters. Here, the dependent variable is attributed by the values of the independent variable. This further determines the unit change of the dependent variable per unit change in the independent variable. Hence, causation is an essential component in the regression analysis.

Hence, investigators must be cautious of the objective as well as interpretation of their result. Further, this investigation recommends to formulate a test statistic on the significance of the correlation coefficient that is less influenced by the sample size. Such a test statistic tends to lower of committing a Type-I error.

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